

Studies on the Condensation Product of Hydroxylamine and Ethyl Acetoacetate

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The condensation product of hydroxylamine and ethyl acetoacetate has been isolated by Rose and Scott¹ following the method of Hantzsch² with slight modification. The compound was identified by them as methyl isoxazolone. Donleavy and Gilbert³ who also prepared the compound by Hantzsch's method, have shown the compound dimolecular for which they proposed a structure of the compound. Subsequently Caramella and Grunanger⁴ have also reported that the compound is dimolecular but with one molecule of water of crystallisation. Jacquier and his coworkers⁵ have supported the dimolecular structure by I.R. and N.M.R., studies. The anhydrous compound is now known as dimethyl-diisoxazolone(I). The present authors have confirmed this view.

Dimethyl-diisoxazolone, prepared by condensing hydroxylamine and ethyl acetoacetate, was recrystallised from hot water and obtained as a white needle-shaped crystalline compound (m.p. 169°–170°). On heating at 105°, the loss in weight corresponded to one molecule of water. [Found : Eqv.wt., 197.9, H₂O, 9.13; N, 14.17; C₈H₈O₃N₂, H₂O requires, Eqv.wt. 198; H₂O, 9.09; N, 14.14%].

The compound (I) may have a tautomeric form (II). It behaves as a weak monobasic acid of moderate strength. By potentiometric titration of its solution in (1 : 1) aqueous-methanol at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$), pka value has been found to be 2.40 at 27°. Its potassium salt and compounds with amines have been reported⁶. But it also forms metal complexes and apparently acts as a monoprotic bidentate ligand. Cu (II), Co (II), Ni (II) and UO₂ (II) complexes with the ligand dimethyl-diisoxazolone (RH) have been

isolated. From analytical data they appear to be MR_2 type of complexes. An indigo-blue colouration with $Fe(III)$ solution has also been observed. Detailed studies are in progress.

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